

DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF HYBRID PHOTOVOLTAIC ELECTRICAL SYSTEM MODULAR TRAINER

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed at the development and evaluation of a Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer, focusing on its suitability to educational curricula and industry standards. Through meticulous conceptualization, design, and construction processes, the trainer was tailored to meet the needs of electrical and electronics education. Feedback from Electronics and Electrical teachers, students, and industry partners revealed strong agreement with the trainer's design, functionality, safety, durability, and instructional applicability. While overall acceptability was consistent across respondent groups, variations emerged in perceptions of instructional applicability, particularly between teachers and students. The findings emphasize the importance of considering diverse perspectives in educational tool design. Furthermore, the alignment of laboratory activities with the Electronics Product Assembly and Servicing (EPAS) NC II curriculum underscores the trainer's relevance in vocational education. Overall, the study affirms the Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer as a valuable resource for enhancing hands-on learning experiences in electrical and electronics education, reflecting its successful integration of educational and industry standards.

Keywords: *Modular Trainer, trainer's design, electrical and electronics education, hands-on learning experience, vocational education*

INTRODUCTION

In the Philippines, education is widely recognized as a catalyst for social change and national progress, as enshrined in Article XIV of the 1987 Philippine Constitution. The constitution emphasizes the importance of science, technology, and education in driving national development. Consequently, schools across all levels play a critical role in equipping students with the necessary knowledge, skills, and attitudes to contribute actively to the country's growth and development.

Quality education hinges on the availability of training materials and equipment, collectively referred to as facilities in educational institutions. These facilities are instrumental in providing high-quality education, as they support effective teaching and learning processes. According to Bajet, et.al (2015), a learning institution's overall facilities, which include its instructional gadgets and equipment, play a major role in providing high-quality education. Specialized equipment becomes even more crucial for schools offering Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) strands. Technical Vocational and Livelihood Schools must provide suitable laboratory facilities and equipment to ensure that students receive hands-on training that simulates real-world industry environments.

Moreover, the Philippine educational system recognizes students' diverse needs and aspirations. After gaining sufficient knowledge, skills, and attitudes, learners are given the opportunity to choose from various curriculum exits, including higher education, middle-level skills development, entrepreneurship, and employment (DepEd, 2018).

The Senior High School TVL track is specifically designed for students seeking immediate employment opportunities after graduation. These vocational courses equip students with the skills and knowledge necessary to obtain certifications relevant to their chosen fields. The importance of technical-vocational education in preparing students for future careers cannot be denied. Technical-vocational education equips students with practical skills and knowledge that are essential for specific industries (Oviawe, 1970). These skills and knowledge are highly valued by employers, as they directly contribute to the productivity and success of businesses. Furthermore, technical-vocational education also provides students with opportunities for entrepreneurship and self-employment.

However, the effective delivery of technical education is hindered by challenges such as a shortage of tools, equipment, and facilities. Inadequate resources can significantly impact students' learning experiences, particularly in technical subjects that require hands-on applications.

Recognizing these challenges, educators often resort to innovative approaches to enhance the teaching-learning process. Despite resource constraints, teachers demonstrate initiative and resourcefulness in improving instructional devices and laboratory equipment for specialized subjects.

One such initiative is the development of a trainer. Using mock-up trainers as teaching tools is a crucial aspect of the teaching-learning process. Pereyras (2020) asserts that acquiring the necessary technical skills and exercises ensures that students will receive a high-quality education in a setting similar to an industrial one. Thus, this study aimed to develop a Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer at Isabela School of Arts and Trades (ISAT). This trainer aims to address the shortage of educational materials and equipment, particularly in the Electronics Product Assembly and Servicing (EPAS) specialization. By providing hands-on experience with renewable energy technologies, the trainer not only enhances students' technical skills but also promotes environmental sustainability.

Additionally, by incorporating a hybrid photovoltaic electrical system modular trainer into technical-vocational education, students can gain hands-on experience and practical training in renewable energy technology (Moses, 2016). This will not only enhance their employability skills and make them more marketable in industries that are shifting towards renewable energy, but it will also contribute to the sustainable development goals of the country. The development of a hybrid photovoltaic electrical system modular trainer for technical-vocational-livelihood students is crucial in equipping them with the necessary skills and knowledge to contribute to the growing demand for renewable energy solutions.

The proposed Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer offers a range of activities aligned with the TESDA National Certificate II for Photovoltaic (PV) System Installation NC II. Through practical exercises such as circuit connections, battery testing, and troubleshooting, students gain valuable experience in solar PV system installation.

By using the Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer, the students can perform different activities like (a) Connection of DC to DC solid state Relay (b) Connection of DC to AC solid state relay (c) Installation of control panel for solar PV system (d) Testing battery charging (e) Series circuit connection of solar panel (f) parallel circuit connection of solar panel (g) Series/parallel circuit connection of solar panel (h) Series circuit connection of battery (i) parallel circuit connection of battery (j) Series/parallel circuit connection of battery (k) Set voltage of low voltage disconnection module (l) Troubleshooting at solar PV system, (m) Circuit connection of automatic transfer switch, and (o) actual measuring of voltage from solar and battery bank.

In summary, the development of innovative teaching tools like the Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer reflects a commitment to providing quality technical education despite resource constraints. By equipping students with practical skills and knowledge, educational institutions contribute to workforce development and national progress.

Research Questions

This research generally aimed to develop and evaluate the acceptability of a Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer as an instructional material or equipment for training and upgrading students' skills in Electronic Product Assembly and Servicing (EPAS) and Electrical Technology at Isabela School of Arts and Trades.

Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the process of developing a Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer?
2. What is the level of acceptability of the proposed Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer in terms of:
 - a. design and construction,
 - b. functionality,
 - c. durability,
 - d. safety, and
 - e. instructional applicability
3. Is there a significant difference in the level of acceptability of the Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer as perceived by groups of respondents composed of teachers, students, and industry experts?
4. What laboratory activities could be performed using the developed Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer?

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a mixed-method research design namely, the Project Development Method (PDM) because the researcher conceptualized the design and specifications of the Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer, and the Descriptive-Evaluative research as he had the device evaluated along specific criteria. Ninety (90) respondents were involved in this study, consisting of fourteen (14) teachers of Electronics and Electrical Technology, six (6) Industry Partners, and seventy (70) Electronics and Electrical Technology students who were currently enrolled in the Trade schools of the City of Ilagan, Isabela for the school year 2023- 2024. They were purposively selected based on their expertise in this particular field of study.

To carry out the research, the researcher drafted a letter and presented the evaluation instrument to be used to the school division Superintendent to secure permission to conduct the study for ethical purposes. After permission was granted, the researcher wrote a letter to the school heads of the different trade schools in the City of Ilagan. After getting the approval, the researcher floated the questionnaires.

The evaluation questionnaire used in the study was adapted from the study of Bartolome (2019) entitled "Industrial Motor Control System Trainer" and of Angangan (2021) titled "Manually- Operated and PLC Ready Motor Control Trainer". The modified instrument let the respondents evaluate the developed trainer as to its design and

construction, functionality, durability, safety, and instructional applicability. The instrument is considered valid and reliable since the two studies mentioned were already published in international refereed journals.

Data gathered were analyzed using weighted mean to know the level of acceptability of this newly developed trainer in terms of *design and construction, functionality, durability, safety, and instructional applicability* and analysis of variance (ANOVA) to compare the responses and evaluations of the respondents in terms of the identified variables. Meanwhile, the five-point Likert's rating scale was used in determining the descriptive meaning of the indicators of the variables used, as shown below.

Scale	Mean Range	Qualitative Description
5	4.20 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)
4	3.40 – 4.19	Agree (A)
3	2.60 – 3.39	Moderate Agree (MA)
2	1.80 - 2.59	Disagree (D)
1	1.00 – 1.79	Strongly Disagree (SD)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

About the Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer

Technical specialists and a variety of writers' writings and publications that are directly related to ideas and operating principles of the Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer were reviewed like Rahman, et. al. (2022) who discussed extensively photovoltaic technology, Myer (2020) who developed a solar modular power with parallel AC and DC wiring, and Rostand, et.al. (2019) who explained about solar automatic transfer switch. The Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer is assembled in a modular board with an electrical system and safety devices for actual performance and shop laboratory uses, the design and implementation of each of the fundamental circuit units and how the program was implemented to, control the plan and perform the required functionality. From the bellow illustration, it can be seen that the significant parts of the system include the following:

- Solar panels / PV array (PV modules)
- Charge controller
- Battery bank
- Inverter
- Disconnecting Switch Devices/ Automatic Transfer Switch
- Safety Devices

Process in Developing Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer

To develop successfully the Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer, the researcher followed the process of conceptualization, design, and construction. In constructing the project, he made sure that the Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer should be suited to the curriculum/subjects. It is appropriate for Electrical and Electronics teachers, students, and industry experts' level of understanding. He also checked the availability of supplies and materials to be used from local stores. And, he made sure that the developed trainer could be manually operated, user-friendly, and suitable for the learners for their practical or hands-on application.

In constructing the project, the researcher prepared the tools materials equipment needed, measured and cut the metallic tubular bars according to their right dimension, and welded the cut tubular bars to their desired dimensions based on the plan of the trainer.

Figure 1. Measuring and cutting tubular

He then ground the surface of welded parts to remove slag and applied buddy filler, applied paint on the surface of the finished frame assembly, cut the plyboard according to the specific dimensions, covered the back of the frame, and assembled it using plywood.

Figure 2. Painting the assembled frame of the trainer

Next, he assembled and mounted all electrical components and devices in the modular boards according to their layout and design. He also attached the modules to the frame assembly and attached the banana jacks to the electrical components mounted inside the modules.

Figure 3. Mounting electrical modules to the assembled frame

Finally, he did the testing. This is the phase where the trainer is put into operation. Before energizing the trainer, the researcher made sure that all electrical components were free from grounded conductors.

Figure 4. The researcher tests the functionality of the newly developed Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer

Level of Acceptability of the Proposed Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer

Tables 1-5 below present the summary of the evaluation of the three groups of respondents on the hybrid photovoltaic electrical system modular trainer. The evaluation results of the hybrid photovoltaic electrical system modular trainer demonstrate robust satisfaction across multiple dimensions.

Table 1. Level of acceptability of the proposed Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer in terms of Design and Construction.

A. Design and Construction	Mean	SD	Description
1. The trainer has a unique design and construction.	4.60	0.49	Strongly Agree
2. The trainer can be easily reproduced for student use.	4.20	0.67	Strongly Agree
3. The trainer has components that are well assembled and visible for easy understanding	4.64	0.50	Strongly Agree
4. The trainer has components that are tough and tension-resistant.	4.47	0.56	Strongly Agree
5. The trainer is strong and in good condition.	4.62	0.49	Strongly Agree
Mean	4.50	0.28	Strongly Agree

In Table 1, the respondents strongly agreed to the unique design and construction of the developed trainer (4.60) as it had well-assembled and visible components for easy

understanding (4.64), and had tough and tension-resistant components (4.47) and was strong and of good condition (4.62).

The grand mean of 4.50 shows the respondents' strong agreement with the overall design and construction of the developed proposed Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer.

This finding is supported by the study of Gonzales, et. al (2022) which found that the developed trainer has well-designed and well-assembled components and construction.

Table 2. Level of acceptability of the proposed Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer in terms of Functionality

B. Functionality	Mean	SD	Description
1. The trainer shows the actual operation of HPESMT	4.71	0.50	Strongly Agree
2. The trainer can serve its purpose and is efficiently	4.59	0.54	Strongly Agree
3. The trainer is easy to operate and maintain.	4.57	0.60	Strongly Agree
4. The trainer can be manipulated by students for easy understanding of concepts.	4.43	0.58	Strongly Agree
5. All components of the trainer work well for the shop activities	4.69	0.49	Strongly Agree
Mean	4.60	0.27	Strongly Agree

As shown in Table 2, functionality emerged as a standout feature of the developed trainer. The three groups of respondents strongly agreed on its efficacy in demonstrating the system's operation (4.71), can serve its purpose efficiently (4.59), is easy to operate and maintain (4.57), can be manipulated by students for easy understanding of concepts (4.43), and all components of the trainer work well for shop activities (4.69). The grand mean of 4.60 indicates that the respondents strongly agreed with the functionality of the developed Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer.

Santos (2019) highlights that the functionality of the trainer gives chances for various activities in shop work concerning practical electronics and electrical circuits through the use and application of active components.

Table 3 exhibits the evaluation of the three groups of respondents in the Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer in terms of Safety.

Table 3. Level of acceptability of the proposed Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer in terms of Safety.

C. Safety	Mean	SD	Description
1. The trainer is equipped with safety and protective devices.	4.51	0.54	Strongly Agree
2. Connectors are insulated to minimize short circuits and electrocution.	4.58	0.58	Strongly Agree
3. The trainer is easy to maintain	4.41	0.61	Strongly Agree
4. The trainer has movable parts which are properly mounted for safety	4.68	0.47	Strongly Agree
5. The trainer components are mounted on a non-conductor material.	4.40	0.59	Strongly Agree
Mean	4.51	0.34	Strongly Agree

In terms of safety features of the developed trainer, the respondents strongly agreed that the trainer was equipped with safety and protective devices (4.51), had connectors that were insulated to minimize short circuits and electrocution (4.58), was easy to maintain (4.41), had movable parts which are properly mounted for safety (4.68), and it had components mounted on a non-conductor material. With a grand mean of 4.51, the respondents strongly agreed with the safety of the trainer.

This finding concurred with the study of Angangan (2021) which found that a proper design and construction of the trainer would prevent risk from happening during actual activity.

Table 4 below reflects the evaluation of the three groups of respondents of the Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer in terms of durability.

Table 4. Level of acceptability of the proposed Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer in terms of Durability.

D. Durability	Mean	SD	Description
1. The trainer power bank can survive in the long run	4.63	0.53	Strongly Agree
2. The trainer components are fixed	4.51	0.54	Strongly Agree
3. The trainer can stay strong for long condition	4.59	0.60	Strongly Agree
4. The trainer wire and conductor used are in good condition	4.62	0.49	Strongly Agree
5. The parts and components can strongly resist tension.	4.54	0.54	Strongly Agree

Mean	4.58	0.26	Strongly Agree
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As can be seen in the table above, the respondents expressed confidence in the proposed Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer since they strongly agreed to its durability as indicated by the grand mean of 4.58.

Specifically, they strongly agreed that the trainer's power bank could survive in the long run (4.63), had fixed components (4.51), could stay strong for long condition (4.59), used wire and conductor in good condition (4.62), and its parts and components could strongly resist tension.

This result implies that the materials, supplies, and components can last long. Further, the result of the study is backed by Velasco's (2018) findings that to develop a trainer or a device, it should be made of durable supplies and materials and should be designed in such a way that it can resist or withstand any weather conditions.

Table 5 presents the evaluation of the three groups of respondents of the proposed Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer in terms of Instructional Applicability.

Table 5. Level of acceptability of the proposed Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer in terms of Instructional Applicability.

E. Instructional Applicability	Mean	SD	Description
1. The trainer is effective for instructional and shop work use.	4.77	0.45	Strongly Agree
2. The trainer is suited to the student's specialization in electrical and electronics subjects for laboratory	4.66	0.48	Strongly Agree
3. The operation and manipulation of the trainer are according to the needed action for each activity.	4.53	0.58	Strongly Agree
4. The trainer can be used to improve the teaching-learning process.	4.66	0.48	Strongly Agree
5. The trainer is suited for TVL Senior High School learners.	4.73	0.47	Strongly Agree
Mean	4.67	0.26	Strongly Agree

As shown by the above data, the respondents strongly agreed with the overall instructional applicability of the trainer with a grand mean of 4.67. In particular, they had strong agreement on the trainer being effective for instructional and shop work use (4.77), its suitability to student's specialization in electrical and electronics subjects for laboratory (4.66), with the operation and manipulation of the trainer following the needed action for

each activity (4.53), could be used to improve the teaching-learning process (4.66), and it is being suited for TVL Senior High School learners (4.67).

The above results are backed by the findings of Milkić, et, al (2018) which show that by using a trainer, students can learn new information and skills about everything under laboratory conditions. Moreover, it was proved that the developed trainer can be a good foundation for the development of new teaching approaches for renewable power academic studies.

In the same vein, Bartolome's (2018) study found that his developed trainer was suitable for addressing the dearth of training equipment used in the school laboratory/workshops thereby indicating its instructional applicability.

Furthermore, Angangan (2021) found out that instructional apparatus and instructional materials could further improve the teaching and learning process thus recommending the development of trainers.

Finally, Tejano (2018) emphasized that using technology in the classroom is an effective way to help students conceptualize concepts by showing them how to do a certain task.

Comparison in the Level of Acceptability of the Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer as Perceived by Groups of Respondents

To determine if there was any significant difference in the level of acceptability of the Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer as perceived by groups of respondents composed of teachers, students, and industry experts, an analysis of variance was employed. The result is presented in Table 6 below.

Table 6. Comparison in the level of acceptability of the Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer among teachers, students, and industry experts

Indicator	F-value	p-value	Comparison	Decision	Remark
Design and Construction	0.99	0.37	p-value > 0.05	Accept null hypothesis	Not significant
Functionality	1.48	0.23	p-value > 0.05	Accept null hypothesis	Not significant
Safety	1.42	0.25	p-value > 0.05	Accept null hypothesis	Not significant
Durability	0.42	0.66	p-value > 0.05	Accept null hypothesis	Not significant
Instructional Applicability	4.63	0.01	p-value < 0.05	Reject null hypothesis	Significant

The analysis shows important insights across various indicators. Firstly, concerning design and construction, the statistical evaluation, with a p-value of 0.37 and an F-value of 0.99, suggests that there was no significant difference in perception among the groups. This indicates a consensus regarding the trainer's design and construction quality.

Similarly, the assessment of functionality reveals a p-value of 0.23 and an F-value of 1.48, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. Consequently, there was no notable distinction in perceptions of the trainer's functionality, indicating agreement among the groups on its operational performance.

In terms of safety, the analysis obtained a p-value of 0.25, alongside an F-value of 1.42, further supporting the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This implies that teachers, students, and industry experts largely share similar views on the safety features of the trainer.

Moreover, concerning durability, the statistical examination yielded a p-value of 0.66 and an F-value of 0.42, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. Thus, there was no significant difference in perceptions of the trainer's durability among the groups. However, a notable difference emerged on instructional applicability, with a p-value of 0.01 and an F-value of 4.63, surpassing the significance threshold. This suggests varied perspectives among the groups regarding the trainer's effectiveness for instructional purposes.

In summary, while agreement prevails among teachers, students, and industry experts regarding the trainer's design, functionality, safety, and durability, disparities exist in their views on its instructional applicability. Further exploration is warranted to discern underlying factors contributing to this variation and refine the trainer's instructional utility accordingly.

Table 7. Multiple Comparison (among the respondents on the instructional applicability of the trainer)

Respondents		Mean Difference	Std.Error	Sig.
Teachers	Students	0.22*	0.07	0.01
	Experts	0.19	0.12	0.28
Students	Teachers	-0.22*	0.07	0.01
	Experts	-0.03	0.11	0.94
Experts	Teachers	-0.19	0.12	0.28
	Students	0.03	0.11	0.94

Table 7 shows the multiple comparisons of the responses of the respondents on the instructional applicability of the modular trainer using Tukey.

The analysis of respondent perceptions regarding instructional applicability of the Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer highlights significant differences in

viewpoints between teachers and students while revealing no notable distinctions between teachers and industry experts, as well as between students and experts. Specifically, the comparison between teachers and students indicates a statistically significant mean difference of 0.22 ($p = 0.01$), suggesting that teachers perceived the trainer more favorably compared to students. Conversely, there were no significant differences in perceptions between teachers and industry experts, nor between students and experts, with p -values of 0.28 and 0.94, respectively. This implies that both teachers and experts, as well as students and experts, held similar perspectives regarding the trainer's attributes.

Laboratory Activities That Could be Performed Using the Developed Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer

The developed Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer comes with a laboratory manual that is based on selected competencies of Electronics Product Assemble and Servicing (EPAS) NC II at Isabela School of Arts and Trades, City of Ilagan. Table 8 below shows the list of laboratory activities that could be performed with a photovoltaic electrocortical system modular trainer.

Table 8. List of Laboratory Activities

	Laboratory Activity
1	Connection of DC-to-DC solid state Relay
2	Connection of DC to AC solid-state relay
3	Installation of the control panel for solar
4	PV system
5	Testing battery charging
6	Series circuit connection of solar panel
7	Parallel circuit connection of solar panel
8	Series/parallel circuit connection of solar panel
9	Series circuit connection of the battery
10	Actual measuring of voltage from solar and battery bank.
11	Parallel circuit connection of the battery

Conclusions

In conclusion, the development and assessment of the Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer have yielded impressive results. Through meticulous conceptualization, design, and construction processes, the trainer has been tailored to meet the needs of both educational curricula and industry standards. The strongly positive feedback from Electronics and Electrical teachers, students, and industry partners underscores the trainer's excellence in design, functionality, safety, durability, and instructional applicability. While overall acceptability was consistent across respondent groups, notable variations emerged regarding instructional applicability, particularly between teachers and students. This suggests the importance of considering diverse

perspectives when designing educational tools. Moreover, the alignment of laboratory activities with the Electronics Product Assembly and Servicing (EPAS) NC II curriculum further solidifies the trainer's relevance in vocational education. Overall, these findings affirm the Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer as a valuable resource for enhancing hands-on learning experiences in the field of electrical and electronics education.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions in this study, the following recommendations are advanced:

1. Continuous involvement of Electronics and Electrical teachers, students, and industry partners in the further development and improvement of the trainer is encouraged. Their feedback is essential for ensuring that the trainer remains relevant and effective.
2. Given the differences in perceptions between teachers and students regarding instructional applicability, consider implementing customizable features or modules that cater to the unique learning styles and needs of both groups.
3. The researcher is encouraged to establish a system for continuous evaluation and iteration based on feedback from users. This will help in identifying areas for improvement and ensuring that the trainer evolves to meet changing educational requirements.
4. The school that uses the trainer should provide training sessions or workshops for teachers to maximize the instructional potential of the trainer. This can help educators make the most of the resources available and enhance the student's learning experience.
5. Collaboration between educational institutions and industry partners to create real-world projects and situations that can be integrated into the training modules is encouraged. This shall provide students with practical hands-on experience and enhance their skill development.
6. The school (ISAT-DepEd) should look into opportunities to align the developed trainer (*Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer*) with other relevant curricula or certifications beyond EPAS NC II to broaden its educational impact and reach a wider audience of learners.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Following ethical standards, this research adheres to principles of integrity, respect, and responsibility towards all participants involved. Before the conduct of the study, the researcher obtained informed consent from the participants, ensuring their

understanding of the study's purpose, procedures, and potential risks. Confidentiality and anonymity were preserved throughout data collection, analysis, and dissemination, safeguarding participants' privacy. Moreover, the researcher made sure that there was no conflict of interest in conducting the study, avoided plagiarism issues, and no bias was made in the interpretation of the results of the study. Finally, he ensured that the findings were used only for the research.

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REFERENCES

- Angangan, Jomel (2021) "Construction and Evaluation of Manually- Operational and Programmable Logic Controller (PLC) Ready Motor Control Trainer With Activity Manual", Marikina Polytechnic College, Sta. Elena, Marikina City (Unpublished Thesis)
- Bajet, M. A., Hidalgo, R. C., & Bajet, N. A. (2015). Design and Development of Electric Motor Controller Trainer: An Instructional Device. *JPAIR Multidisciplinary Research*, 20, 55-67.
- Bartolome, E. A. (2020). Development and Acceptability of an Industrial Motor Control System Trainer. *International Journal of Advanced Trends in Computer Science and Engineering*, 9(1.3), 435-439.
- Department of Education (2018). DepEd order no. 169: guidelines for senior high school, Technical Vocational and Livelihood Track.
- Gonzales, E. A. N., & Muyot, N. B. (2022). Portable Solar Powered Outdoor Charging Station With The Application Of Servo Motor In Sunlight Tracking System With Light Detection Relay Sensor. *International Journal of Science, Technology & Management*, 3(4), 950-958.
- Rostand, F. K., Mustapha, M. M., Adabara, I., & Hassan, A. S. (2019). Design of an automatic transfer switch for households solar PV system. *European Journal of Advances in Engineering and Technology*, 6(2), 54-65.
- Myer, S. (2020). *U.S. Patent No. 10,573,176*. Washington, DC: U.S. Patent and Trademark Office.
- Milkić, Ž., Čukarić, A., Štatkić, S., & Maksimović, G. (2018). Characteristics of a doubly-fed asynchronous generator applied in wind turbines. *ЕКОНОМИКА пољопривреде*, 65(1), 229-241.
- Moses, K. M. (2016). Improving the Quality and Competence of Technical vocational education and training output through vocational school cooperation with industry: A case study of Uganda. *Proceeding of the International Mechanical Engineering and Engineering Education Conferences (MEEEC 2016)*.

- Oviawe J. I. (1970). Revamping technical vocational education and training through public-private partnerships for skill development. *Makerere Journal of Higher Education*, 10(1), 73–91. [Crossref](#)
- Pereyras, J. G. (2020). Development of an electrical wiring installation trainer. *International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research*, 9(3), 4458-4461.
- Rahman, Y. A., Fauzi, R., & Sarjan, M. (2022). Module trainer of photovoltaic integrated low voltage grid (PV-LV grid) with a variety loads. In *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering* (Vol. 1212, No. 1, p. 012041). IOP Publishing.
- Santos, J. S. (2020). Development and Evaluation of AC/DC Basic Electronics and Electrical Circuit Connection Trainer. *Solid State Technology*, 63(5).
- Tejano, L. L. (2018). Off-grid Solar Power Mock-up. *Asian Journal of Business and Technology*, 1(1).
- Velasco, Raymund C., (2018) “Customized Multi-Purpose Photovoltaic Powered Device with Automatic Transfer Switch”, Isabela State University- Ilagan Campus. (Unpublished Thesis)